

Equitable Information Portal Design for Mobilizing Salmon Knowledge

Meeting Report

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Introduction

Salmon are integral to the culture, economy, and ecology of many communities in Arctic and sub-Arctic regions. Currently, salmon information, data, and knowledge is gathered and managed across different agencies, organizations, researchers, and communities, and housed across multiple data portals and hubs, making it difficult for interested parties to access and use this information. This decentralization has led to inequities in access to data, where members of local communities may not have access to crucial information about their natural resources, impeding timely decision making and hindering potential collaboration.

Recognizing this gap, Research Networking Activities for Coordinated Observations (RNA CoObs) organized a working session titled “Equitable Information Portal Design for Mobilizing Salmon Data,” which occurred in Anchorage, Alaska from April 23-25, 2024. The session aimed to better understand the need for equity in Arctic observing systems, with a specific focus on salmon data. The session brought together a diverse group of salmon system experts, including state and federal agency managers and scientists, tribal representatives and members, members of fishing communities, academics, and data scientists, to distill a vision, assess needs, and consider implementation pathways for a salmon information portal. The goals of the working session included conducting a high-level needs assessment, designing documents and features for the portal, identifying targeted portal users, listing data to be included, and strategizing engagement with data holders.

Key Takeaways

The working session revealed a diverse range of potential users, use-cases, and information for a salmon knowledge portal. Identified users included researchers, managers, tribal and local community members, educators, and journalists, with potential information spanning from novel research on salmon and the environment to guidance for decision-support, policy advocacy, communication, and fishing practices. Users and use cases were classified into local, state, and national and international levels, with some users and use-cases overlapping multiple levels.

Throughout the meeting, participants emphasized the importance of maintaining data equity, data sovereignty, and informed consent as well as ensuring that a portal would be broadly accessible. As a result, participants felt the narrow concept of 'data' should be broadened into 'knowledge'. This expansion in language emphasizes the importance of integrating Indigenous knowledge and the inclusion of synthesized data products, plain language products, info-sheets, and visualizations built with and for non-research audiences. Participants also discussed the need for timely data availability, especially for access by local community members. This includes the need for salmon researchers to understand what active and proposed projects are being conducted, where they are being conducted, and the need to share funding information.

In terms of who would maintain a salmon knowledge portal, there was strong support for a neutral third party to develop a knowledge sharing system, building on existing partnerships such as those emerging from the International Year of the Salmon.

Participant Recommendations

At the end of the working session, participants discussed recommendations and next steps for designing a salmon knowledge portal, which we have grouped into the following themes:

Funding and Resource Allocation

- Create inventory of salmon counting and observing locations and assets with associated funding support, including an analysis of change over time

Indigenous and Tribal Knowledge

- Design a portal that promotes and respects data equity, data sovereignty, and informed consent
- Ensure continued Indigenous involvement and support in management and academia in ways that benefit Indigenous communities
- Combine contextual, Indigenous, and local knowledge in a story map format to provide context for data sets, such that Indigenous knowledge holders in particular see themselves in the data and information products

Data and Research Needs

- Share discovery level metadata for salmon related projects and observing sites
- Propose and seek support for the Alaska Board of Fisheries to publish all proposals and board actions in a structured and categorized data set following each meeting (in addition to the text documents they already release)
- In addition to the documents they already release, propose and seek support or incentives that would allow State management agencies to clean and append annual salmon escapement, harvest, and age, sex, and length (ASL) data to an integrated, published data product in a public repository like the KNB (<https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/>) each year

Accessibility and Inclusive Terminology

- Communicate data in plain speech
- Show data through visualizations of what each community is doing and will do to improve related to management priorities and limitations
- Make salmon data more equitably accessible to researchers, community members, policy makers
- Create summary infographics (Ex: 1-pagers on key concepts such as escapement-based management or Genetic Stock Identification)

Incentives and Engagement

- Need incentives to promote the use and maintenance of a portal
- Have project funders require that data be in a repository
- Encourage agencies to deposit data annually in public archives
- Make sure that the value of a data and knowledge portal is illustrated to foster wider adoption
- Show the benefits of a knowledge portal to the people of Alaska so that agencies can then add it to priority statements
- Foster more collaboration between data users and producers at project outset
- Need agencies to prepare MOUs/MOAs for data access (e.g., Alaska Department of Fish and Game)

Partnerships

- Develop partnerships with groups such as the Indigenous Sentinels Network, Native Biodata Consortium (<https://nativebio.org/>), Tamamta Program (<https://www.tamamta.org/>), Alaska Native Science and Engineering Program (ANSEP, <https://www.ansep.net/>)
- Approach consortiums like the Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS, <https://aoos.org/>) or State of Alaskan Salmon and People (SASAP, <https://alaskasalmonandpeople.org/>) to organize, centralize and provide access to data
- Approach the Alaska Resource Library and Information Services (ARLIS) or similar library to organize and provide open datasets

Portal Design and Management

- Start the process by focusing on a single region with a pilot/mockup
- Recognize on the landing page that there are missing data; there is a lot of data that is difficult to represent and distribute
- Include focus on data portal interoperability
- Have the National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis (NCEAS), Sustaining Arctic Observing Network (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing Data Systems (ROADS) and/or a similar effort create a data archive/portal federation or coalition for salmon knowledge

Next Steps

Building on the priorities identified during the workshop, next steps include the following:

- Design and gather feedback for salmon knowledge and information portals that would be useful to community, academic, tribal, agency, and other interested audiences.
- Prototype and test ideas about these portals with these constituent communities
- Outline a roadmap for design, development, and sustainability of a salmon data portal for these communities
- Define the scope of a salmon counting asset inventory (see recommendation under “Funding and Resource Allocation”) and explore the feasibility of hosting such an inventory at the Arctic Observing Viewer portal (<https://arcticobservingviewer.org/>)
- Explore options for an in-depth assessment of a salmon counting asset inventory for a particular subregion, such as Bristol Bay or Yukon watershed, in partnership with Indigenous organizations and local experts
- Gauge the emerging salmon knowledge portal needs of the SAON ROADS Salmon Expert Panel during in-person sessions at the RNA CoObs meeting, Fairbanks August 28, 2024

Conclusion

By the end of the working session, the need and support for a centralized salmon knowledge portal was clear. Creating such a portal would not only facilitate timely decision making and foster collaboration, but ensure that everyone from local communities to international researchers have access to critical salmon knowledge. The recommendations from this working session provide a roadmap forward (see next steps above); however, the success of such an initiative relies on the collective efforts of the community.

Workshop Participants

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References for Graphics and Photos

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